

Bab edh-Dhra

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Bab edh-Dhra^c is an archaeological site located in Jordan, notable for its over 20,000 burials and large influential settlement traditionally associated with the Biblical town of Sodom. While the site does have evidence of occupation dating back as early as the Paleolithic, Neolithic and Chalcolithic Periods, the Early Bronze Age remains are most informative for Near Eastern History because they exemplify shifts in ancient burial customs, the initial drive toward urbanism and the inherent early struggles associated with transitioning to a sedentary lifestyle. Bab edh-Dhra^c, located in Transjordan along the southeastern section of the Dead Sea about 240 m below sea level, is bound by the Wadi Kerak, which served as a fresh water source as well as a defensible cliff protecting the town's inhabitants. Surveys of the region beginning in the 1920s identified Bab edh-Dhra^c as a noteworthy site which led to excavations commencing in the 1960s led by Paul W. Lapp, and subsequent expeditions continued through the 1970s and 1980s. Excavations of the Early Bronze Age revealed that early on burials dominated the landscape, and later on the site was the location of a large fortified town. The Early Bronze Age IA tombs at Bab edh-Dhra^c provide key insights into ancient burial practices and beliefs about the dead. Over 60 Early Bronze Age IA shaft tombs have been investigated, most comprising of multiple chambers often circular in shape and each covered by a domed or flat roof. Each chamber held piles of disarticulated bones from multiple individuals with skulls lining the side of the tomb. The chambers also included several ceramic vessels with slash or incised design, and some additional grave goods such as stone bowls, clay figurines, mace heads, and jewelry. Round mudbrick burial houses containing remains of multiple individuals were introduced later on during the EB IB, and a small settlement also arose at the site during this time. Following a brief period of possible destruction and abandonment, the EB II Period site saw a population increase and the town exhibited features such as large public buildings, a silo and an enclosure wall. The EB II population continued the burial practices of the EB I and constructed more funerary buildings that housed primary and secondary burials as well as pottery and other artifacts. While the burial practices are most noted in the earlier parts of the Early Bronze Age, the focal point later becomes the urban development characteristic of the Early Bronze Age III in the region. The population at the site continued to increase and the site was fortified with a 7m-wide mudbrick wall with a stone foundation that encompassed nine acres of occupation that could have housed around 1,000 people. Within the walls there were domestic quarters, monumental buildings and a "sanctuary" in the southern part of the town that contained a courtyard with a stone altar and tools most likely used for butchering animals. Evidence for occupation was also found outside the city walls and remnants of barley, wheat, and sheep and goat bones were uncovered in excavations. During this time period, the dead were placed in rectangular mudbrick burial buildings, called Charnel Houses, and accompanied by pottery, figurines, and other objects. The end of the early Bronze Age saw an abandonment and deterioration of the large EB III town. Occupation shifted to the countryside surrounding the former town and a ceremonial area containing an altar and animal horns sat within the ruins. The abandonment of the city and preference for rural occupation is a trend seen throughout the region at the end of the Early Bronze Age. While we do not know the ancient name of the site, the ruins have traditionally been linked to the biblical site of Sodom and the story of its demise found in Genesis 19 based on its location and evidence of conflagration. However, this theory has been contested mainly because of the questionable historicity of the story and the occupation dates to an earlier time than the bible story would have taken place. Some

have argued that the biblical story could have been formulated to explain the ancient ruins of the city visible along the Dead Sea. Preservation of the site and proper documentation of the finds, especially from the tombs, is hindered by the extensive looting that has taken place at Bab edh-Dhra^c for over a century. Many of the site's artifacts have entered the illegal antiquities market. The local government and archaeologists are working to document the artifacts, enact measures to protect the site and recover the stolen objects of this important Early Bronze Age site. Artifacts from the burials can also be found in museums throughout the world, thus providing access for many people interested in understanding ancient burial practices. The ancient site of Bab edh-Dhra^c continues to provide key insights into our understanding of ancient burial practices and shifts toward early urbanism as archaeologists work to study, protect, and preserve the culturally valuable material from the site.

Date Range: 3300 BCE - 2000 BCE

Region: Bab edh-Dhra

Region tags: Jordan, Eastern Mediterranean, West Asia, Levant

This map represents the location of the archaeological site of Bab edh-Dhra.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Schaub, R. Thomas, and Walter E. Rast, eds.: Bab edh-Dhra': Excavations in the Cemetery Directed by Paul W. Lapp (1965–1967), Reports of the Expedition to the Dead Sea Plain, Jordan 1. Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns 1989
- Source 2: Schaub, R. Thomas. "Bab Edh-Dhra'". In *The New Encyclopedia of Archaeological Excavations in the Holy Land*, edited by Ephraim Stern, Ayelet Levinson-Gilboa, and Joseph Aviram, 1:130–36. Jerusalem: The Israel Exploration Society, 1993.
- Source 3: Rast, Walter E. and R. Thomas Schaub, eds. Bâb edh-Dhrâ'. Excavations at the Town Site (1975–1981). Reports of the Expedition to the Dead Sea Plain, Jordan 2. Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 2003.
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- Source 2: • Chesson, Meredith S., and R. Thomas Schaub. "Life in the Earliest Walled Towns on the Dead Sea Plain: Numayra and Bab Edh-Dhra'". In *Crossing Jordan: North American Contributions to the Archaeology of Jordan*, edited by Thomas Evan Levy, P. M. Michèle Daviau, Randall W. Younker, and May Shaer, 245–52. London: Equinox, 2007.
- Source 3: • Graves, David E. *The Location of Sodom: Key Facts for Navigating the Maze of Arguments for the Location of the Cities of the Plain*. Toronto: Electronic Christian Media, 2016
- Source 1: Rast, Walter E. "Patterns of Settlement at Bab Edh-Dhra'". In *The Southeastern Dead Sea Plain*

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– Source 2: • Schaub, R. Thomas. "Southeast Dead Sea Plain". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of Archaeology in the Near East*, edited by Eric M. Meyers, 5:62-64. Oxford,,: Oxford University Press, 1997.

– Source 3: Rast WE. 1999. Society and mortuary customs at Bab edh-Dhra. In: Kapitan T., editor. *Archaeology, history and culture in Palestine and the Near East*. Atlanta, GA: Scholars Press. p. 164-182.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: http://expeditiondeadseaplain.org/?page_id=27

– Source 1 Description: Expedition Dead Sea Plain

– Source 2 URL: <https://www3.nd.edu/~nsfbones/nsfbones/Dhra.html>

– Source 2 Description: Bab edh Dhra Bioarchaeology

– Source 3 URL: <https://followthepotsproject.org/>

– Source 3 Description: Follow the Pots Project

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

– Illicit

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1960 - 1980

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Bab edh Dhra Excavations

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Illicit

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1900 - present

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Water source
- Body of water (as distinct from source)

↳ Type of elevation

- Canyon

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Terracing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Mound

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– I don't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass
– Field doesn't know

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: stone foundations

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– No

↳ On the inside:

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: incised design on pots

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– I don't know

Notes: Decoration found on pots and other artifacts in burials.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Graves had several grave goods including ceramic and stone pots, jewelry, maces, etc.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: pots, jewelry, maces, stone objects

↳ Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Other

– Other [specify]: Charnel House

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– I don't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
 - Yes [specify]: animal bones found in sanctuary

- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - No

- ↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
 - No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
 - Yes

- ↳ Other

– Other [specify]: pottery, stone vessels, jewelry, maces

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Field doesn't know

Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Function for water management:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Burial location

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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Reference: Bab edh-Dhra, Schaub, Thomas R.. Bâb Edh-bhrâ: Excavations in the Cemetery Directed by Paul W. Lapp (1965-67) (reports of the Expedition to the Dead Sea Plain, Jordan, Vol. 1). Edited by Walter E. Rast. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 1989.

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